

EFFECT OF SURFACE TREATMENT ON MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF PLAIN GLASS WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES: REPORT OF A ROUND ROBIN TEST I

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SUMMARY: A round-robin test programme has been carried out to characterize the mode I interlaminar fracture behaviour of E-glass woven fabric reinforced vinyl ester matrix composites. Special emphasis has been placed on the effect of silane coupling agent on the stability of interlaminar crack propagation and the fracture toughness. Twenty laboratories were invited to participate in this programme. Each laboratory was supplied with composite laminates of thickness of its own choice which were fabricated by the Society for Interfacial Materials Science (SIMS), and conducted the tests to its own procedures. The results submitted by each laboratory are presented, and the observations and implications are discussed.

KEYWORDS: E-glass woven fabric reinforced vinyl ester composites; mode I interlaminar fracture toughness; silane coupling agents; interface; stability of crack propagation

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates made from glass woven fabrics and vinyl ester resin have been developed for printed circuit board (PCB) applications, specifically aimed at low-end to mid-range systems. To improve the efficiency of stress transfer across the fibre-matrix interface glass fibres are commonly treated with silane coupling agents [1]. There are several factors which influence the chemical, physical and mechanical properties of the interface. They include the silane structure in treating solution and its organo-functionality, the drying conditions, and the morphology and chemical composition of the fibre surface. The concentration of coupling agent has been found to be a critical factor in determining the mechanical performance and fracture behaviour of the composite. An interface with strong adhesion is expected to give a composite with good shear, compressive and off-axis strengths, and the silane agents applied on glass make the composites more durable in hygrothermal environment [2].

The Society for Interfacial Materials Science (SIMS) has been established in 1993 with the aims to enhance our fundamental understanding of the science in composite interfaces of various nature by bridging the gap between material science, mechanics and manufacturing of composite materials, and to encourage the interactions between the research communities from academia and relevant industries for international collaborations in applied research and development. As one of the most important activities organized by the SIMS, the round robin test (RRT) program was developed to study the effect of fibre surface treatment on the mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced vinyl ester matrix composites. In the first RRT program, tensile and bending strengths and moduli were measured of the composites containing woven fabrics treated with five different silane coupling agents: namely 0.01, 0.4 and 1.0 wt% methacryl silane (designated as M0.01, M0.4 and M1.0, respectively), methanol washed 0.4 wt% methacryl silane (MW0.4) and 0.4 wt% epoxy silane (E0.4).

Table 1 gives the average values of the results which were presented at the 10th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-10) held in August 1995 [3]. The composites containing M0.01 had the lowest strength both in tension and bending. An increase in methacryl silane concentration resulted in improvement of these strengths. The tensile modulus was found to be relatively insensitive to the type and concentration of silane agents, whereas an increase in methacryl silane gave rise to marginal enhancement of bending modulus. Washing the treated fibres using methanol enhanced to a certain extent both the strength and modulus. Composites containing E0.4 displayed relatively lower strength than those containing fibres with methacryl silane treatment of the same concentration.

Following the success of the first RRT programme, twenty major laboratories were invited worldwide to participate in the second RRT, among which fifteen laboratories have completed the tests when this paper was written, see Table 2. The major aim of the present programme was to determine the effect of silane treatments on mode I interlaminar fracture behaviour. It is generally accepted that delamination represents the weakest failure mode, and is considered to be the most prevalent life-limiting failure modes in laminate composites. As such, ever-increasing attention has been directed toward proper characterization of the failure mode as well as to improve the durability against delamination.

Table 1 Strengths and moduli of glass woven fabric reinforced vinyl ester matrix composites measured in the weft direction¹². (Mean values \pm standard deviation)

Type and concentration of silane agent	Strength (MPa)		Modulus (GPa)	
	Tension	Bending	Tension	Bending
Methacryl silane 0.01wt%	270 \pm 21	372 \pm 20	19.5 \pm 5.2	18.1 \pm 1.5
0.4wt%	318 \pm 16	431 \pm 19	19.6 \pm 5.1	18.8 \pm 1.6
1.0wt%	329 \pm 31	444 \pm 40	20.2 \pm 5.2	19.7 \pm 1.9
Methanol washed Methacryl silane 0.4wt%	338 \pm 13	452 \pm 23	20.4 \pm 5.0	19.4 \pm 0.9
Epoxy silane 0.4wt%	321 \pm 32	380 \pm 27	20.3 \pm 5.0	19.3 \pm 1.1

Table 2 Participating laboratories.

Laboratory	Contact
Bournemouth University, UK	H. Saidpour
Chinese Academy of Science, China	T.X. Mao
CNAM / ITMA, France	C. Bathias
Ecole des Mines de Douai, France	P. Krawczak
Furukawa Electric Institute of Technology, Hungary	S. Pinter
Hong Kong University of Science & Technology, Hong Kong	J.K. Kim
Katholic University of Leuven, Belgium	I. Verpoest
Kyoto Institute of Technology, Japan	H. Hamada
Nanyang Technological University, Singapore	C.Y. Yue
Syonan Institute of Technology, Japan	T. Tanimoto
Technical University of Hamburg-Harburg, Germany	K. Schlute
University of Kaiserslautern, Germany	J.K. Karger-Kocsis
University of Liverpool, UK	W.J. Cantwell
University of Sydney, Australia	L. Ye

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials and Test Specimen

Test materials were fabricated by the SIMS, and were supplied to the participating laboratories. Materials including fibres, matrix materials, silane coupling agents and fabrication procedures of the composite laminates employed in the present program were essentially the same as those used in the first RRT programme. The E-glass plain woven fabrics contained 44 (warp) x 34 (weft) strands per 2.5 cm x 2.5 cm square area (WE18W,

supplied by Nitto Boseki Co, Ltd., Japan). Each strand consisted of 400 filaments of 9 mm in diameter. The matrix material was made from an unsaturated vinyl ester resin (Ripoxy R806; Showa High Polymer, Japan) which was polymerised with 0.7 phr. methyl-ethyl-ketone (MEK) peroxide. The coupling agents used were g-methacryloxy-propyltrimethoxysilane (methacryl silane, A-174; Nippon Unicar Co., Japan) and g-glycidoxy-propyltrimethoxysilane (epoxy silane, A-187; Nippon Unicar Co., Japan). The aqueous solutions of silane coupling agents were acidified with acetic acid at pH 4.0. Five different combinations of silane coupling agents were used for fibre surface treatment: 0.01, 0.4 and 1.0 wt% methacryl silane (designated as M0.01, M0.4 and M1.0 respectively); methanol washed 0.4 wt% methacryl silane (MW0.4); and 0.4 wt% epoxy silane (E0.4). The glass fabrics were dipped into the aqueous solutions of the silane agents, which were subsequently squeezed between rollers and were dried for 10 min at 110°C.

The laminates were prepared by hand lay-up such that all warp strands were aligned in one direction, and were cured for 48 h at room temperature, followed by post cure for 3 h at 80°C and for 2 h at 150°C in an oven. A 40 mm thick polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) film was inserted at the mid-plane of the laminate as an initial crack during the lay-up. The average fibre volume fraction was found to be approximately 42.6% [3]. The instructions on the laminate thickness and the length of precracks were specified by each participating laboratory.

Each participating laboratory cut the laminates to its desired sizes and geometry. Typical double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen is illustrated in Figure 1. In most laboratories, specimen edges were painted with white correction liquid on which fine lines were scribed at certain intervals to assist locate the advancing crack tip. Either aluminium tabs or piano hinges were bonded to the specimens to allow gripping and loading the specimen in tension. Crack length was monitored with the corresponding load and displacement recorded simultaneously. Compliance values were taken in the interrupted unloading and reloading experiments. Each laboratory calculated the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} , using its own data reduction schemes. Table 3 gives the details of the test specimen dimensions and test conditions used by each participating laboratory.

Data Reduction Schemes

There are basically four different linear elastic fracture mechanics methods to analyze the data obtained from the load-displacement records [4]: namely, (i) the area method; (ii) the compliance method; (iii) the load method; and (iv) the displacement method. Because the details of the relevant equations for G_{IC} values and the measurement techniques are given elsewhere [4], the same will not be repeated here. Due to the effects of various aspects of the practical DCB tests, such as end rotation and deflection of the crack tip, effective shortening of the beam and stiffening effect of the beam due to the presence of the end tabs, modified compliance methods have been proposed as standard methods.

Figure1 Geometry of double cantilever beam specimen.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

Figure 2 shows typical load-displacement curves of the interlaminar fracture tests obtained for laminates containing fibres with different silane agent treatments. Based on the stability of crack propagation these curves can be classified into two groups: M0.01 and E0.4 for stable fracture; and M0.4, M1.0 and MW0.4 for unstable fracture. For the laminates in the first group, the load increased in a linear manner to a maximum, which was followed by a gradual decrease with further crack extension [5]. The crack propagated in a slow and stable manner. In sharp contrast, for the specimens M0.4, M1.0 and MW0.4, the load-displacement curves displayed "saw-teeth" type behaviour where the rising portion and the abrupt drop of the load corresponded to stable crack re-initiation and crack arrest after rapid, unstable crack propagation, respectively. The unstable fracture behaviour did not allow the measurement of the propagation G_{Ic} values.

Figure 2 Typical load - displacement curves with five different surface treatments:
 (a) methacryl silane 0.01wt%; (b) methacryl silane 0.4wt%; (c) methacryl silane 1.0wt%;
 (d) methacryl silane 0.4wt% / methanol washed; (e) epoxy silane 0.4wt%.

Table 3 Specimen dimensions and data reduction schemes of each participating laboratory.

Laboratory	Width W	Thickness 2h	Length L	Crack length a	Cross-head speed (mm/min)	Data reduction scheme*
1	20	3	125	50	2.5	A
2	25	4	200	48	2.0	B
3	25	2	100	30	1.0	B
4	20	3	125-180	25-80	1.0	B
5	10	3	270	20	5.0	B and F
6	20	4	130	20	1.0	B
7						
8	25	4	100	20	1.0	C
9	12.5, 25	3	125	25	1.0	D
10	25	4	100	30	1.0	C
11	20	5	200	55	2.0	B
12	20	4	125	50	1.0	B
13	20	4	200	50	5.0	B
14	25	3.8	170	65	0.5	A and E

*A = modified compliance method (ASTM 5528 - 94a); B = corrected beam theory (ESIS Protocol); C = modified compliance method (JIS K7086); D = load method; E = displacement method; F = area method.

In the modified compliance calibration method specified by ASTM D5528-94a, the G_{Ic} value for crack propagation is given by:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 P^2 C^{2/3}}{2 \alpha_1 b h} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load and a_1 is obtained directly from the slope of a/h versus $C^{1/3}$ plot. In the corrected beam theory recommended by the European Structural Integrity Society (ESIS) TC4 Group as a protocol in 1990, G_{Ic} is determined by:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{n P \delta}{2 b a} \quad (2)$$

where n is the slope of the log-log plot of the compliance versus crack length (C vs Da) curve. The initiation value of G_{Ic} is taken at the force corresponding to the initial non-linearity of the load-displacement curve. The G_{Ic} value specified by JIS K7086 is calculated based on the equation:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 P^2 (b C)^{2/3}}{4 h b^2 \alpha_2} \quad (3)$$

where a_2 is determined empirically.

Figure 3 gives the initiation and propagation G_{Ic} values from all participating laboratories. Due to the unstable crack propagation as discussed above, only the initiation G_{Ic} values are reported for specimens M0.4, M1.0 and MW0.4. It is found that the initiation G_{Ic} value decrease in general with increasing the methacryl silane concentration: in particular it is found that the G_{Ic} value is higher for M0.01 than for M1.0 (nearly 100%) except for a few isolated cases such as Laboratories 3, 4 and 13. Washing of the treated fibres with methanol did not change much the overall fracture behaviour (maximum of 40% and often below 10%), with largely varying initiation G_{Ic} values for different laboratories.

It is presumed that in composites containing M0.4 and M1.0 silane agents a thick and densely cross-linked, brittle interlayer is formed at the fibre-matrix interface region which was mainly responsible for the brittle, unstable crack propagation. In composites with M0.01 and E0.4, a more ductile, compliant interlayer is developed, giving rise to a stable, ductile crack growth. The concentration of the coupling agents has a drastic effect on interlaminar fracture behaviour of the laminates. An increase in methacrylate silane agent showed deteriorating effect on the stability of crack propagation and thus the fracture resistance of the laminate. Contrary to the expectation, removal of the loosely bound interlayer of the silane agent by washing with methanol did not improve greatly the overall fracture behaviour of the laminates. From the comparison between the specimens M0.4 and E0.4 which contain the same silane concentration, it is noted that the epoxy silane yielded significantly higher for a majority of laboratory and stable fracture resistance than methacryl silane. It is found that G_{Ic} values at initiation and propagation are higher for M0.01 specimens than for E0.4 specimens, except for two isolated cases (lab.5 and 6 at initiation).

Figure 3 Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of glass woven fabric / vinylester composites: (a) initial values; (b) propagation values.

Figure 4 shows typical crack growth resistance G_{IC} curves for specimens M0.01 and E0.4. G_{IC} values increased significantly with increasing crack length. This behaviour is ascribed to the presence of fibre bridging in the wake of the propagating crack in woven fabric laminates [6]. The fibre bridging contained the growth of the cracks, enhancing the stability of crack propagation. Certainly, the extent of the fibre bridging phenomenon is influenced by the fibre surface treatment, as it modifies the nature of interface bonding and the mechanical properties of the interface region.

Figure 4 Typical crack growth resistance G_{IC} curves for specimens:
(a) M0.01 and (b) E0.4.

Examinations of the fracture surfaces using scanning electron microscopes suggested the followings:

- (i) For M0.01 and E0.4 specimens, the fibres were exposed on the fracture surface without resin adhering onto them.
- (ii) For M0.4 and M1.0 specimens, much of the fibre surface was covered by the matrix resin, in particular on the fracture surface corresponding to the unstable crack propagation.
- (iii) Much more fibres were covered with resin in specimens MW0.4 than M0.4.

The foregoing observations suggest that:

- (i) Crack propagation along the fibre-matrix interface region is relatively slower and more stable than crack propagation in the matrix material away from the interface.
- (ii) Change of the crack path occurred from the interface region to the matrix with increasing the methanol silane concentration. Wash of silane treated fibres with methanol further encouraged this behaviour, aggravating the instability of crack propagation.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A round-robin test programme has been undertaken to characterize the mode I interlaminar fracture behaviour of glass woven fabric-vinyl ester matrix composites containing five different silane coupling agents on the fibres. All test materials were fabricated in a laboratory of the SIMS, and were supplied to the participating laboratories. The format of the programme was maintained loose in an effort of assess the current practice of the test method and the variability of test results affected by different specimen dimensions and data reduction procedures. For each test, the general procedures were pretty much similar, and major

differences were identified in the specimen dimensions and data reduction procedures used by some laboratories. The differences in the details of the tests and data reduction procedures resulted in a high degree of data scatter between the laboratories, albeit the general trend of interlaminar fracture toughness influenced by different silane agents were much consistent. To decrease the data scatter, the standards such as ASTM, JIS, ESIS etc. will be harmonized within the next 3 or 4 years under the cover of an ISO standard (ISO / CD.2 15024). It is considered that such movement will direct toward the helpful method which exchanges the concepts of many researchers and improve the durability against delamination in laminate composites.

M0.01 and E0.4 specimens displayed stable, slow crack propagation, whereas M0.4, M1.0 and MW0.4 specimens showed rapid, unstable crack propagation. As expected the G_{Ic} values increased with crack extension for both the specimens containing M0.01 and E0.04 which showed stable crack propagation. In this RRT programme, an over 100% variation was observed by all the laboratories on initiation values of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness with different silane treatments. These variations were higher than that of the results previously obtained for tensile and bending tests (below 25% on moduli and below 10% on strengths) and reported in the first RRT programme. Moreover the mode I method makes it possible to separate the cracks initiation and the cracks propagation phenomena on which the interface quality has a specific incidence. Hence, mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests seem to be interesting method to investigate the fracture behavior of composite materials with interfaces of different qualities.

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